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PERSPECTIVE OF RURAL TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

ПЕРСПЕКТИВА РАЗВИТИЯ СЕЛЬСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

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Abstract. The article is devoted to actual problems of effective development of rural tourism in Uzbekistan. Currently, there are 10,865 villages in Uzbekistan. Each of these villages has a unique tourist destination. The government attaches great importance to creating new jobs in rural areas and improving the living standards of the population. Rural tourism is one of the directions of the economy that can be used in this direction. When organizing rural tourism, the following points should be taken into account: first, that each village is a set of unique cultural, material and natural resources. Secondly, these are cultural landscapes, rural life and other resources.

In conclusion, it is concluded that it is necessary to liberalize rural production; guide to ensure spiritual, physical recreation in the city; guide for rural culture, traditions and protection of the rural environment.

Аннотация. Статья посвящена актуальным проблемам эффективного развития сельского туризма в Узбекистане. В настоящее время в Узбекистане насчитывается 10865 деревень. Каждая из этих деревень имеет уникальное туристическое направление. Правительство придает большое значение созданию новых рабочих мест в сельских районах и повышению уровня жизни населения. Сельский туризм — это одно из направлений экономики, которое может быть использовано в этом направлении. При организации сельского туризма должны учитываться следующие моменты: во-первых, каждая деревня — это совокупность уникальных культурных, материальных и природных ресурсов. Во-вторых, это — культурные ландшафты, сельская жизнь и другие ресурсы.

В заключении делается вывод, что необходима локализация сельского производства; руководство по обеспечению духовного, физического отдыха в городе; руководство для сельской культуры, традиций и защиты сельской среды.

Keywords: agriculture, rural tourism, education, agriculture, culture.

Ключевые слова: сельское хозяйство, сельский туризм, образование в сельском хозяйстве, культура.

An important role and importance of rural tourism development are unique in our country. Experience of developed European rural tourism shows that these countries entered the development of rural tourism more than 50 years ago. That is why the first place in the world of

rural tourism development is the international model of the rural tourism development of the French countryside, the UK model, the German model and the Italian model of rural development.

Which of the models for rural tourism development in Uzbekistan now is more memorable and more convenient? When we examine the structure and operation of these models, the application of them to the development of rural tourism does not create any problems, but it's easy. Because the diversity of the main resource and tourist resources for the development of rural tourism is higher than in the above-mentioned European countries.

The main problem of rural tourism development in our country is that we have not yet understood the purpose and purpose of rural tourism.

Decree No. PF-4861 of December 2, 2016 “On measures to ensure the rapid development of the tourism industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan” by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev has created a fundamental breakthrough in the development of tourism in our country, the foundation of a new stage, and prospective reforms. Presidential Decree [3].

- “Accelerated development of tourism in the country, more comprehensive and effective utilization of existing tourism potential, visit of other potential tourism species along with traditional cultural and historical tourism, ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic, sports, medical, accelerated development of business tourism and other types of tourism, development of children, youth and youth tourism, family tourism, social tourism for the elderly, integrated development of internal, entrance and exit tourism Regional development and implementation of the program”.

This decree serves as the main program of regional and regional development of tourism in all spheres of tourism. It is time to start scientific research on the nature of our villages, the world of flora and fauna, the use of climatic features in tourism.

Our villages and auls are located in different nature zones and altitudes, so the peoples of these villages have been preserved for centuries in the mozy's, United, indefinite, lifestyle, national traditions, national production, national culture and to see national games, national values, learn is essential to our self-awareness. The history, culture, economy, spiritual and educational life of our country are closely connected with the villages. That is why the first president of our country, I. A. Karimov, stated that “if the village is prosperous, our land will prosper, and our lives will be better” [1].

Currently, there are 10865 villages in Uzbekistan. Each of these villages has a unique tourist destination. It is untenable that the organization and development of tourism, which is widely used in tourism activities in our country, especially in rural areas, have a great impact on our socio-economic life. At the moment, our government attaches great importance to creating new jobs in rural areas and improving the living standards of the population. Development of tourism in rural areas is important and it has potential. These options include:

- low cost of rural services and accommodation services;
- freedom to watch and participate in national games;
- 2–2.5 times cheaper than urban settlements and catering services;
- Ecological cleanliness of rural areas;
- Availability of ecologically clean food products;
- Preservation of the ancient national cultural heritage and traditions of our people;
- Rich variety and diversity of attractive tourist resources, national characteristics, diverse types of services, and so on;

- Preservation of the national product development (national handicrafts, defective goods, etc.);
- Secondly, we have the resources of the following types of tourism in our villages;
 - Specially protected areas — near the national parks of Uzbekistan, the state nature reserve, the state nature reserve, nature monuments, the location of our villages;
 - Historical and archaeological tourism resources — historical monuments, historical sites, archaeological ruins, findings;
 - Ethnographic tourism resources — Ancient local lifestyle, national folklore, traditions, culture, ceremonies, national games;
 - Agricultural and agro-tourism resources — orchards, farming, cultural landscapes and agricultural works, horticulture, village views and construction;
 - Sources of religious and travel tourism — sacred places, graves of saints, medicinal springs, various religious rituals;
 - ecological tourism resources — the location of rural areas in all natural and geographical regions of our country (mountain, for third, desert, steppes, reservoirs);
 - recreational and recreational tourism resources — hostels, health centers, resorts, mineral waters, springs, forests, forests, forests, waterfalls, river banks;
 - Farmer's working style and lifestyle — farming, fodder preparation, crop production and sale.

In the organization of forest tourism, all of the above-mentioned tourism resources are cumbersome, work together and take up any tourist for a longer period of time. That is why European countries have started developing rural tourism since the 60's of the last century. First of all, we are seriously considering the development of rural tourism in the country and start research in this direction is one of the most important and urgent tasks in the development of national tourism.

Currently, the flow of tourists in rural Europe is about 60 million tourists in European countries. Tens of thousands of tourist companies and touristic organizations are successfully operating in France, Germany, England and Italy. We are just beginning to explore the essence, goals and objectives of rural tourism in our country.

The following analysis shows how useful the development of rural tourism in Uzbekistan and compliance with the economic policy of the state in the implementation of the current socio-economic reforms in the free market. On the basis of rural tourism development, we can achieve great successes in key issues such as addressing unemployment in rural areas, increasing agricultural production, improving the rural economy, organizing trade, organizing national production, and strengthening international solidarity.

In our country, first of all, the development of rural tourism requires the development of a state program and the second is the creation of a strategic plan. Scientists, experts, public figures, public figures on the issues of rural tourism development plan, state program, management structure, financing system, opportunities in rural areas, tourist resources in rural areas, influence of rural population on tourist's visit to villages, impact on rural socio-economic life, — The economists of the field are always exposed to popular science articles [2].

The development of rural tourism in the country should be understood as the rest of the urban population in the countryside. The basis for coming to such a conclusion is that we have studied the geography of rural tourism in Europe, which is a very strong tourism and rural tourism. Even the European Union has a great negative impact on the development of rural tourism: Northern

European rural tourism, Central European rural tourism, Southern European rural tourism, and rural tourism in Eastern Europe.

We need to study international technologies and programs in the area of development of rural tourism, taking into account that the country has not yet started serious scientific research. In the development of rural tourism, we have to study the EU's "Strategic Plans for the Development of Rural Tourism". Based on this strategic plan, the rural tourism development program includes: For us this program can be very important;

- Improving the legal and regulatory framework for rural tourism development;
- Providing free information on all rural tourism information to potential tourists and information bureau of developing networks;
- financial support of dehqan farms participating in the program;
- allocate targeted funds to improve rural infrastructure;
- applying the incentive policy for farmers and encouraging the establishment of preferential taxes;
- search for investors to implement projects;

Forest tourism, ecotourism and recreational tourism are indissolubly linked to each other. Organization of domestic and international ecotourism flows in the development of tourism in rural areas of the country, creation of new promising directions will undoubtedly be one of the most promising directions of national tourism. Because, when analyzing the development of international ecotourism, international ecotourists are primarily interested in national parks, nature preserves and unique nature gardens, natural biodiversity and endemic plants and animal species.

All the registered tourism resources are located near our villages. The second direction in international ecotourism is interest of plants and animals in the International Red Book of States. In the third area of international ecotourism ecotourists are interested in the international biosphere reserves, reserves and specially protected natural areas in each country. The resources of this ecotourism are also in our villages.

There are 4 qualified colleges in the country, which train highly qualified specialists in the field of tourism, Bukhara, Tashkent, Urgench state universities and Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service. Taking into account the potential of this labour force and the accumulated experience in the development of tourism, tourism is a top priority in tourism, which will allow the people of our country to relax, develop and develop rural tourism, raising the economy of the country.

At the initial stage of development of rural tourism in Uzbekistan it is necessary to develop organizational and economic mechanisms of organization and management of rural tourism. At the second stage, it is planned to develop legal-normative laws on development of rural tourism on the basis of these organizational and economic mechanisms. In the third stage, based on the legal-normative laws of rural tourism development, registration of tourist resources in our villages, preparation of their description, we have to create touristic facilities in tourism facilities [5].

The most important is to ensure the literacy, informatization of the rural population in the development of rural tourism, and to educate rural children in tourism colleges, tourism education institutes and universities.

One of the most pressing issues in the development of rural tourism in our country is the development of touristic routes and touristic excursion routes to tourist resources in rural areas. Development of tourist routes for tourism development, as well as the introduction of tourists from

touristic goods after tourist promotion on the domestic and foreign markets are among the norms of tourism.

When it comes to services of touristic and touristic routes, its customers, tourists, become apparent. Therefore, in the development of rural tourism in our country, it is crucial to study tourist demand, tourist offers and tourist consumption, and this issue is topical.

Conclusion:

1. We need to perceive each village as their unique cultural, material and natural resources, cultural landscapes, rural life and other resources.

2. Together with the development of rural tourism, our state solves the most important and actual socio-economic problems of our country. We plan to develop rural tourism in the following directions:

- Provide a lot of opportunities for rural tourism to address employment opportunities in rural areas;
- Development of rural tourism specialized in raising the socioeconomic status of the rural population;
- Localization of rural production;
- Guidelines for the provision of spiritual, physical rest of the city;
- Guidelines for rural culture, traditions and the protection of the rural environment.

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